

Copper(II) complexes are green crystalline, whereas zinc complexes are white crystalline compounds. They have relatively low melting points and are soluble in acetone in which medium the low molar conductance values indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic moments of copper(II) complexes are in the range of 1.78-1.82 B.M. showing the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for a $3d^9$ ion.

Infrared spectra: In case of the thenoyltrifluoroacetone chelates two bands appear around 1605 and 1580 cm^{-1} region of which the high frequency band can be assigned to carbonyl stretching vibration. There is also an absorption band around 3500 cm^{-1} attributable to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of the coordinated water molecule. In the nitrogen base adducts the carbonyl stretching band shifts to 1620 cm^{-1} in case of zinc complexes whereas two bands appear at 1615 and 1605 cm^{-1} in case of copper(II) complexes, alongwith the disappearance of O-H stretching band due to the water molecule. Further, most of the absorption bands of the free nitrogen ligands are shifted in the base adducts, providing evidence of bonding through the nitrogen atom of the bases. In case of the pivaloyltrifluoroacetone chelates, carbonyl stretching appears as a broad absorption band at 1600 cm^{-1} , due to the presence of $\delta(\text{OH})$ in this region alongwith the $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ appearing at 3480 cm^{-1} . In the mixed ligand complexes the carbonyl absorption appears as a sharp band around 1620-25 cm^{-1} region instead of the broad band of the *bis* chelate and the absorption due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ disappears, thus indicating the coordination of the nitrogen ligands to the metal ion. This has been further substantiated by the observations^{1,2} of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ around 390-440 and 280-310 cm^{-1} regions, respectively. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ shifts to high frequency region in the base adducts and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ shifts to low frequency region compared to the simple chelates. Further, compared to the non-fluorinated β -diketone chelates and the base adducts, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ in the present compounds shifts to high frequency region and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ to low frequency region.

In the visible electronic spectra of copper(II) chelates and their base adducts one broad absorption band has been observed. $\text{Cu}(\text{tta})_2$ showed absorption at 680 nm ($\epsilon=30$), whereas in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{pta})_2$ the band was observed at 670 nm ($\epsilon=35$). In the base adducts, the absorption band was observed around 690-710 nm region with an increase in the intensity of the band ($\epsilon=60-80$). This is in agreement with many earlier observations. Thus in general there is^{1,2,15} a low frequency shift of the absorption band and increase in intensity of the band on adduct formation compared to the simple *bis* chelates.

Hence the base adducts of copper(II) and zinc β -diketonate are presumably penta-coordinated compounds formed by the coordination of one molecule of the nitrogen base to the metal *bis* chelates. To verify that the base adducts are actually five coordinated monomers rather than 6-coordinated dimers,

the molecular weights of the compounds $\text{Cu}(\text{tta})_2(\text{Q})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{pta})_2(\text{Q})$ were determined by vapour pressure osmometric method in benzene. The observed molecular weights are 602 and 554, calculated values being 634.92 and 582.88, respectively indicating the complexes to be monomeric. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data of the zinc complexes, these are possibly five-coordinated compounds similar to some earlier reported^{1,6} complexes.

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Determination of Stability Constants of Some Metal Complexes of 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-5-methylchalkone Oxime (HMMCO)

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THE formation constants of some bivalent metal ion chelates with 2-hydroxychalkone and 2-hydroxy-5'-methylchalkone in 70% v/v ethanol-water mixture were reported by Swamy *et al*¹. Khadikar *et al*² also studied the formation constants of some bivalent metal ion chelates with 2'-hydroxychalkone in 60% v/v dioxane-water mixture. The present work deals with the determination of successive stability constants of complexes of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalkone oxime (HMMCO) with some transition metal ions in 50% dioxane-water mixture at 25° and

$\mu=0.2 M$ (KNO_3). HMMCO has also been used by us to prepare metal chelates for studying their tentative geometry²⁻⁴ and in the extraction of some metal ions⁵.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. The ligand HMMCO was prepared by the known method⁸. Metal nitrates were dissolved in double distilled water and metal contents were estimated volumetrically by titrating against standard EDTA solution using suitable indicator.

The experimental method employed consists of pH titration of the following three mixtures, in three different vessels⁹, thermostated at 25°, against standard 1.0 M NaOH solution: (A) $-1.92 \times 10^{-2} M$ HNO_3 ; (B) $-(A) + 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand (HMMCO) and (C) $-(B) + 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution. KNO_3 solution was added to each mixture to maintain ionic strength at $\mu=0.2 M$ and the total volume was adjusted to 100 ml in each case with the solvent. A 50% v/v dioxane-water mixture was used as the solvent.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand stability constant of HMMCO was determined by plotting \bar{n}_A vs pH. From this plot the $\log K^H$ was determined as 12.12, which is in good agreement with the value reported earlier⁵.

During metal solution titration, precipitation was observed in Co(II) and Ni(II) systems at pH 7.5, while in the Cu(II) system no precipitate was observed. The stability constants of the metal chelates were determined using Bjerrum-Calvin pH meter titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁶. The various methods (half \bar{n} value, least squares method, interpolations at various \bar{n} values) were used to compute stability constants. The values of stability constants obtained by the three methods were nearly the same. Table 1 contains the stability constant values obtained by interpolation at various \bar{n} values for Co(II) and Ni(II) systems and by least squares method for Cu(II) system.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Complex	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_n$
Co(II)	7.41	—	7.41
Ni(II)	7.73	—	7.73
Cu(II)	10.58	8.88	19.46

It can be concluded from the results in Table 1 that the order of the stability constants ($\log K_1$) of the complexes in the present investigation is $Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II)$ which is in harmony with Irving Williams order⁷. $\log K_2$ values of Ni(II)-HMMCO and Co(II)-HMMCO systems could not be

obtained due to precipitation during titration at higher pH (>7.5). The order of stability observed in the present investigation is in good agreement with the earlier workers^{1,2}.

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Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Trivalent Praseodymium and Neodymium Complexes with Glutamic acid : A Polarographic Study

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STABILITY constants and thermodynamic parameters of rare earths complexes with glutamic acid have been determined by different authors using different methods¹⁻⁴. A survey of literature reveals that no work has so far been done on rare earths complexes with glutamic acid by the polarographic method. The stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of rare earths complexes with glutamic acid, obtained by the polarographic technique, are being reported here.

Experimental

A. R. grade chemicals were used to prepare all the solutions. Stock solutions of praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) were prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity of metal oxides in minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid (AnalaR). The metal solution was standardised with EDTA⁵. The overall concentrations of potassium chloride, gelatin and